

Parallel synthesis and herbicidal activity of pyrethroid library

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A pyridine-containing pyrethroid library of 255 compounds was conveniently constructed using parallel synthesis. The library was screened by high through-put screening (HTS), and further study was focused on the compounds with initial bioactivities. The results suggest that some compounds could be potential herbicides.

In the past several decades, pyrethroids have been widely applied as insecticides and fungicides. However, development of new pyrethroid derivatives as new active agrochemicals is still known as an attractive field. To the best of our knowledge, serial synthesis of pyrethroid for study on their herbicidal activity, has not been done. As compared to traditional methods for biological activity, screening in pharmaceutical and agrochemical areas, parallel synthesis recently developed has significantly improved the screening efficiency for building libraries of new serial compounds with molecular diversity¹⁻⁷. In this paper, we combined two active structures of chrysanthemic acid and pyridine to develop a pyridine-derived pyrethroid library for their potential herbicidal activity using parallel synthesis.

Results and discussion

In our design, a new pyrethroid library was constructed by reaction of three kinds of chrysanthemic chlorides with pyridine-containing alcohols and amines (Scheme 1) for screening of their herbicidal activities.

Scheme 1

The acyl chlorides, i.e., 3-(2',2'-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylate acid chloride ($R = A$), 3-(2',2'-dimethylvinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylate acid chloride ($R = B$), and 2,2,3,3-tetramethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylate acid chloride ($R = C$) were made in 0.5 mol/L stock solutions in dichloromethane. The desired alcohol and primary amine were also made in 0.5 mol/L stock mixture solution with the same equivalent of triethylamine in dichloromethane. All reactions were carried out in 8 ml vials packed in a reaction tank with a circulating cooling bath.

In our library, 126 esters and 129 amides were totally prepared through parallel synthesis (Table 1); the reactions were monitored by TLC. In order to evaluate the efficiency of the library synthesis, some reactions were randomly sampled for GC and HRMS analysis. As shown in Table 1, the purity for most of the products was above 85% by GC analyses. Acyl chlorides were used as the synthetic reagents for simplifying the workup procedure, because small amount of residual starting materials could be removed by base washing. Indeed, good to excellent results were achieved for most of the compounds in our library synthesis.

In the bioactivity screening of the library, all compounds were screened by HTS (high through-put screening) for their herbicidal activities in the first step against *Echinochloa crusgalli* (Barnyardgrass), *Oryza sativa* (Seeded paddyrice), *Brassica alba* (White unestard), *Lepidum sativum* (Peppergrass), *Lemna minor* (Duckweed) and *Avena fatua* (Wild oat) in Bayer CropScience AG. Some compounds have showed good activity against the targets (Table 2). Compounds 2 and 3 showed 100% toxicology effect on ECHCG at 100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and compound 7 with 100% effect on LEMMI under optical evaluation at 5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, respectively.

Further studies on the compounds with primary activity

Table 1. Examples of acylating reaction for the generation of pyrethroid library

Compd. no.	Alcohol or Amine	R	HRMS (M+H) ^a		Purity (%)
			Calcd.	Found	
1	3-(3-Hydroxypropyl)pyridine	A	328.08656	328.08859	>99
2	2-(Aminomethyl)pyridine	A	299.07124	299.07325	87.6
3	2-(2-Aminoethyl)pyridine	A	313.08690	313.08654	87.8
4	3-(Aminomethyl)pyridine	A	299.07124	299.07063	98.7
5	5-Amino-2-methoxypyridine	C	249.15975	249.15790	89.2
6	2-Amino-5-bromopyridine	A	362.96611	362.96973	91.5
7	2-(3-Hydroxypropyl)pyridine	A	328.08656	328.08693	90.3
8	2-Amino-5-chloropyridine	C	253.11022	253.11011	>99
9	3-Amino-2-chloropyridine	C	253.11022	253.11024	>99
10	2-Amino-6-methylpyridine	B	259.18099	259.18096	94.1
11	2-Aminoethylpyridine	C	233.16484	233.16383	68.4
12	2-Amino-5-methylpyridine	A	299.07124	299.07110	36.7
13	3-(Hydroxymethyl)pyridine	C	234.14886	234.14886	56.0
14	2-(Hydroxymethyl)pyridine	A	300.05526	300.05351	>99
15	4-(Hydroxymethyl)pyridine	C	234.14886	234.14964	68.4
16	2-Chloro-3-hydroxypyridine	B	280.10923	280.10988	83.5
17	2-Aminopyridine	C	219.14919	219.14880	>99
18	2-Amino-4,6-dimethylpyridine	B	273.19614	273.19566	91.8
19	4-Amino-2-chloropyridine	C	253.11022	253.10994	>99
20	2-Amino-4-methylpyridine	A	299.07124	299.07154	85.2

^aEach compound was analyzed by HRMS within 10 ppm error in monoisotopic mass.

Table 2. High through-put screening results

Compd. no.	Test conc. (μmol/L)	LEPSA (%)	ECHCG (%)	LEMMI(FL) (%)	LEMMI(OP) (%)
2	100	0	100	0	0
3	100	0	100	0	0
7	5	0	0	0	100

% The toxicology effect on the target.

LEPSA: *Lepidum sativum* (Peppergrass), ECHCG: *Echinochloa crusgalli* (Barnyardgrass), LEMMI: *Lemma minor* (Duckweed), FL: Fluorescence evaluation, OP: Optical evaluation.

in the second step were focused on ECHCG, and other screening items such as ORYSW, AVEFA and LEMMI at 1000 g/ha. All targets were tested under their three stages of ERDE VA (pre emergence test in soil), ERDE NA (post emergence test in soil) and HYDRO VA (pre emergence test in water). The screening results were summarized in Table 3. Compound 7 showed no activity at this step.

As shown in Table 3, the results revealed that compounds 2 and 3 had different bioactivities against three targets of different stages. In the test of ECHCG, compound 2 showed the best activity of 60% toxicology effect on the target at

HYDRO VA in the three tested stages. While the rested two stages have 40% toxicology effect on the target at ERDE VA and 20% at ERDE NA, respectively. Compounds 3 showed no activity against ECHCG under the test. In the test of ORYSW, compound 3 showed 20% toxicology effect on the target at both ERDE VA and ERDE NA while compound 2 had 20% at the stage of HYDRO VA only. Meanwhile, both of them displayed same activity of 20% toxicology effect on AVEFA at ERDE NA.

In conclusion, a pyridine-contained pyrethroid library was conveniently constructed using parallel synthesis

Table 3. Further study of bioactivity of compounds **2** and **3** at three stage^a

Compd. no.	ORYSW (%)		AVEFA (%)		ECHCG (%)	
	2	3	2	3	2	3
HYDRO VA	20	0	–	6	0	0
ERDE VA	0	20	0	0	40	0
ERDE NA	0	20	10	10	20	0

^aThe tests were performed at 1000 g/ha concentration. % : The toxicology effect on the target.

ORYSW : *Oryza sativa* (Seeded paddyrice), AVEFA: *Avena fatua* (Wild Oat), ECHCG : *Echinochloa crusgalli* (Barnyardgrass),

HYDRO VA : pre emergence test in water, ERDE VA : pre emergence test in soil, ERDE NA : post emergence test in soil.

method. Some compounds were found to have potential herbicidal activities. Through HTS, compounds **2** and **3** had activity on ECHCG while compound **7** had activity on LEMMI; further screening showed compounds **2** and **3** had some herbicidal activities at different stages.

Experimental

Acid chlorides were prepared by reflux of acids and thionyl chloride and distillation; other starting materials were commercially available. GC analysis was performed on Agilent-4890D (FID, Agilent technologies, U.S.A.). HRMS analysis was carried out on a Mariner-TOF 5303 (APCI, Applied biosystem, U.S.A.). Herbicidal activity screening was taken out by Bayer CropScience AG.

Library synthesis : For a typical reaction, alcohol or amine stock mixture solution (2 ml) was transferred into an 8 ml vial. After cooling to -5° with continuous vibration for 30 min, acid chloride (2 ml) was added into the vial.

The reaction temperature was gradually warmed to ambient temperature and kept vibration overnight. TLC detection showed the reaction was complete. Dichloromethane (1 ml) and saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 solution (2 ml) were added to the vial with vibration for another 20 min at ambient temperature. The organic layer was isolated and washed with water (2×2 ml), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The mixture was filtered and volatiles were removed *in vacuo*

to afford the product.

Bioactivity screening : *Echinochloa crusgalli*, *Oryza sativa*, *Brassica alba*, *Lepidum sativum*, *Lemma minor* and *Avena fatua* were selected as the test targets. The HTS was performed in the first step. Detailed studies on some compounds with initial activity after HTS were performed in the second step including tests in soil and water at 1000 g/ha.

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